

**A Five-Item Conflict Handling Measure (CHM)
for Situational Conflict Handling
Validation Note 1 in Germany**

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Abstract

Conflict-handling approaches vary across individuals and situations. The dual-concern model describes such variation along the concern for oneself and the concern for the conflict partner, resulting in five prototypical conflict styles (obliging, dominating, avoiding, compromising, and integrating). Existing instruments primarily assess trait-like preferences rather than how people handle a specific conflict situation. To address this gap, we developed the five-item Conflict Handling Measure (CHM). This validation note provides initial evidence for the CHM's construct validity in a large sample of German adults ($N = 2,396$). We examined correlational patterns with existing trait conflict style measures and German operationalizations of dual-concern, empathy, and the Dark Triad. The correlational profile was consistent with theoretical expectations, supporting convergent and discriminant validity of the CHM. We encourage replication and further validation work.

Context

Individuals differ in how they approach interpersonal conflicts (Tehrani & Yamini, 2020). Such differences are commonly conceptualized within the dual-concern model (Blake & Mouton, 1964), which suggests that different approaches arise from variations in the concern for oneself and the concern for the conflict partner (Blake & Mouton, 1964; Rahim, 2002). Building on this framework, a range of measures has been developed to assess trait-like conflict styles as indicators of interindividual differences (Ben-Yoav & Banai, 1992; De Dreu et al., 2001; Filsecker et al., 2020; Geppert et al., 2026; Kilmann, 2018; Weider-Hatfield, 1988). The most influential operationalizations distinguish five styles: dominating, integrating, obliging, compromising, and avoiding (Kilmann & Thomas, 1977; Rahim, 2002; Weider-Hatfield, 1988).

To date, most operationalizations assess either trait-like styles or broad conflict orientations. What is largely missing is a tool that focuses on conflict handling at the level of a concrete, experienced conflict situation. To address this gap, we developed a concise five-item measure in plain German. The Conflict Handling Measure (CHM) assesses situational conflict handling with each item intended to capture one of the five established conflict styles.

The Conflict Handling Measure (CHM)

Conflict Handling Measure (CHM) – German Version

Frage [Mit Bezug zu einem vorher definierten Konflikt]:

Wie würden Sie Ihren Umgang mit dieser Auseinandersetzung beschreiben?

Nr.	Beschreibung	Herangehensweise
1	Ich habe versucht, Konfrontationen bewusst aus dem Weg zu gehen.	Vermeiden
2	Wir haben gemeinsam geschaut, was jedem wichtig ist, und so versucht, ein Ergebnis zu finden, das für alle richtig gut passt.	Integrieren
3	Ich habe mich nach den Erwartungen der anderen Person gerichtet und entsprechend Zugeständnisse gemacht.	Nachgeben
4	Ich bin nicht von meinen Interessen abgerückt und habe alles versucht, um mich durchzusetzen.	Dominieren
5	Ich habe versucht, mit der anderen Person halbwegs einen Kompromiss auszuhandeln.	Kompromiss

Antwortoptionen: 0 = Nein, gar nicht. – 1 = Nein, überwiegend nicht. – 2 = Eher nicht. – 3 = Eher ja. – 4 = Ja, überwiegend schon. – 5 = Ja, auf jeden Fall.

Conflict Handling Measure (CHM) – English Translation

Question [with reference to a previously defined conflict]:

How would you describe the way you handled this disagreement?

No.	Description	Handling Approach
1	I tried to deliberately avoid confrontations.	Avoiding
2	Together, we looked at what was important to each of us and tried to find an outcome that really suited everyone well.	Integrating
3	I went along with the other person's expectations and made concessions accordingly.	Obliging
4	I did not back away from my interests and tried everything to get my way.	Dominating
5	I tried to negotiate a compromise with the other person, more or less.	Compromising

Response Options: 0 = No, not at all. – 1 = No, mostly not. – 2 = Rather not. – 3 = Rather yes. – 4 = Yes, mostly. – 5 = Yes, definitely.

Methods

In 2026, we recruited a German adult online sample (18-90 years) according to national quotas for age, gender, and education via the panel provider Bilendi. Respondents who failed embedded quality checks, exhibited implausibly rapid completion time, or could not recall a concrete conflict situation were excluded. The final analytic sample consists of $N = 2,396$ German adults (54.2% women, age: $M = 46$, $SD = 15.28$).

Participants received instructions to recall a specific interpersonal conflict that had occurred within the prior 12 months. To aid memory retrieval, participants were also provided with concrete examples (e.g., everyday disputes with a partner regarding child-rearing, finances, or vacation planning). Participants then indicated how they had handled this situation, using the CHM.

To evaluate evidence for the CHM's construct validity (i.e., nomological network, convergent, and discriminant validity), we administered the CHM alongside the Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory 2 – German Version (ROCI-II-D; Bilsky & Wülker, 2000), the German Conflict Style Screener (COSTY; Geppert et al., 2026), a brief German dual-concern operationalization (question: *What did you orient yourself towards in this conflict?*, concern for oneself: *In my approach to this conflict, I oriented myself towards my own goals and needs*, concern for the other: *In my approach to this conflict, I oriented myself towards the goals and needs of the other person*. Response format: 4-point Likert-scale), the German Dark Triad Dirty Dozen (Küfner et al., 2015), a German Big Five Personality Trait screening measure (Rammstedt et al., 2004), and the German adaptation of the Basic Empathy Scale (Heynen et al., 2016). We then conducted correlational analyses, using Spearman's rank-order correlation due to the single-item-per-approach format of the CHM. We expected the CHM items to be positively associated with their trait-like counterparts from ROCI-II-D (Bilsky & Wülker, 2000) and COSTY (Geppert et al., 2026). We expected cooperating approaches (i.e., compromising and integrating) to be associated with empathy and the dominating approach to

be positively associated with the Dark Triad. We also explored associations with the dual-concern items. Measurement statistics and results from correlational analyses are presented in Table 1.

Results

Table 1.
Measurement Statistics and Bivariate Correlations with the Conflict Handling Measure in German Adults (N = 2,396).

Variable	Descriptive Measurement Statistics						CHM Correlations: Spearman's ρ				
	Min	Max	M	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	Av	In	Ob	Do	Co
CHM_Av	1	6	3.37	1.53	-.03	-.97	1	0.03	.34**	-.17**	.08**
CHM_In	1	6	3.54	1.53	-.19	-.93	0.03	1	.36**	-.12**	.57**
CHM_Ob	1	6	3.32	1.45	-.08	-.84	.34**	.36**	1	-.42**	.39**
CHM_Do	1	6	3.56	1.47	-.08	-.79	-.17**	-.12**	-.42**	1	-.16**
CHM_Co	1	6	3.99	1.39	-.54	-.25	.08**	.57**	.39**	-.16**	1
Self-Concern	1	5	3.76	1.08	-.80	0.21	-.17**	-.08**	-.22**	.38**	-.07**
Partner-Concern	1	5	2.86	1.17	0.03	-.74	.17**	.36**	.43**	-.27**	.34**
ROCI-II_Av	1	5	3.18	0.88	-.21	-.41	.39**	-.06**	.20**	-.02	-.02
ROCI-II_In	1	5	3.9	0.64	-.91	2.26	-.03	.22**	.08**	-.02	.29**
ROCI-II_Ob	1	5	3.49	0.66	-.56	1.18	.19**	.14**	.30**	-.06**	.18**
ROCI-II_Co	1	5	3.85	0.63	-.80	2.09	0.04	.18**	.13**	-.02	.28**
ROCI-II_Do	1	5	2.94	0.86	-.06	-.40	-.06**	.14**	0.03	.24**	.07**
COSTY_Av	1	5	3.18	0.88	-.15	-.19	.33**	-.07**	.14**	-.05*	-.07**
COSTY_In	1	5	3.86	0.77	-.77	1.3	-.00	.16**	.09**	-.05*	.21**
COSTY_Ob	1	5	3.27	0.82	-.15	0	.21**	.07**	.26**	-.08**	.11**
COSTY_Co	1	5	3.73	0.76	-.42	0.39	-.03	.16**	.09**	-.03	.25**
COSTY_Do	1	5	2.81	0.94	0.09	-.37	-.09**	.10**	-.03	.24**	.05*
Dark Triad	1	9	3.12	1.57	0.8	0.32	0.03	-.03	0.01	.18**	-.07**
Narcissism	1	9	3.33	1.87	0.54	-.53	.05*	0.02	.07**	.13**	-.01
Psychopathy	1	9	3.07	1.7	0.84	0.26	-.00	-.07**	-.05*	.17**	-.12**
Machiavellianism	1	9	2.96	1.82	0.98	0.36	0.04	-.03	0.02	.15**	-.07**
Cogn. Empathy	1.2	5	3.98	0.6	-.47	0.36	0.03	.11**	.07**	-.03	.18**
Affect. Empathy	1	5	3.82	0.67	-.51	0.32	.10**	0.03	.12**	-.14**	.13**

Note: CHM = Conflict Handling Measure, ROCI-II = Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory II, COSTY = Conflict Style Screener, Av = avoiding, In = integrating, Ob = obliging, Co = compromising, Do = dominating, cogn = cognitive, affect = affective, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Interpretation

We posit that the correlational patterns are largely in support of the CHM's construct validity. As expected, the conflict handling approaches captured by the CHM showed consistent positive correlations with corresponding trait-like styles measured by the ROCI-II-D (Bilsky & Wülker, 2000) and the COSTY (Geppert et al., 2026). Given that the CHM relies on single-item indicators and targets situational (rather than trait-like) handling, we interpret these associations as consistent with convergent validity.

Additional convergent validity evidence is provided by the dual-concern correlations. Consistent with the theoretical framework (Blake & Mouton, 1964; Rahim, 2002), obliging and avoidance correlated negatively with self-concern. Obliging had the numerically strongest negative association with self-concern and highest with partner-concern, whereas dominating showed the opposite numerical pattern. The cooperating approaches (integrating and compromising) displayed more intermediate correlations. Nomological networks of integrating and compromising appear theoretically reasonable (e.g., positive correlations with cognitive empathy and partner-concern). As anticipated, dominating also depicted positive correlations with the Dark Triad, whereas in support of discriminant validity, non-dominating styles were largely unrelated to the Dark Triad. Limitations of the current report include its reliance on self-report data, which are susceptible to response and recall biases. In addition, the correlational design precludes causal inferences.

We posit that overall, correlational pattern supports the CHM's construct validity. This validation note therefore delivers first evidence for the construct validity of the novel tool. We recommend researchers to further examine its psychometric properties.

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